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**Status and Determinants of Child Undernutrition in Kangra District,
Sub-Himalayan Himachal Pradesh, India**

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ABSTRACT

Background: Higher than national average of wasting rate in children under five years in the Himachal Pradesh state despite unusually high level of women's education and coverage of maternal-child health services was an enigma. Assessing and understanding the determinants of undernutrition in the first 1000 days of life was considered essential for appropriate policy direction. **Methodology:** A nutrition survey, using both the quantitative and qualitative methods (limited to ICDS, health providers, panchayat leaders and spouses) was undertaken. **Results:** Despite 95 % of 949 women surveyed having completed school education, 34.4% weighed <45 kg and 7.4% had height <145 cms while 21.4% births were LBW. Undernutrition was noted to be set as early as before 6 months with 44.2% children underweight, 38.6% stunted, and 21.4% wasted. Poor maternal, infant, and young child feeding (MIYCF) practices were the key contributory factors. **Conclusion:** Survey presents evidence to direct attention to strengthen MIYCF practices in the critical first 1,000 days of life, including ensuring establishing 'effective' techniques for exclusive breastfeeding practices in infants under 6 months.

Key-words: Undernutrition 0-6 months; maternal infant child nutrition; preconception nutrition; maternal, infant and young child feeding (MIYCF) practices; 'effective' exclusive breastfeeding practices, determinants of undernutrition; breastfeeding techniques, complementary feeding; first 1000 days of life.

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Introduction

Child undernutrition influences brain development, IQ levels and school performance and overall development. Analysis of under 5 years mortality in India indicates child and maternal malnutrition is the predominant risk factor for 68.2% of under - 5-deaths and 83.0% of neonatal deaths¹. Nutritional status of population and development are interrelated with 12 of the 17 Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) being influenced by nutritional status². As per the national survey 2019-21,³ nutrition situation of children in Himachal Pradesh, India is rather grave with higher than national average of wasting rate in children under five years. Moreover, an increase in the percentage of stunted children has been reported in 9 of the 12 districts between 2015-21.^{3,4} This trend is noted despite the state's relatively better performance in key development indicators for women, such as high school education completion, low fertility rates, minimal adolescent marriages, and consistently high coverage of maternal and child health services, including institutional deliveries.

Additionally, the state has strong water and sanitation facilities, further highlighting the paradox of rising stunting rates in the face of these favorable underlying conditions. With such a positive situation, it was considered imperative to assess the maternal-child nutrition situation and explore the determinants of child undernutrition with a view to strengthen the existing HP state policy “*Mukhya Mantri Bal Suposhan Yojana*”.

A study was thus conducted to assess the nutritional status of women and young children in the critical first 1000 days of life, along with newly-married women, who are considered to be at a high risk of undernutrition. The aim was to provide evidence-based recommendations for a package of interventions for revisiting the existing state policy to improve maternal, infant, and young child nutrition (MIYCN) status in the progressive Indian state of Himachal Pradesh.

Materials and Methods

Study area, design and sample: This study was conducted by Public Health Nutrition and Development Centre (PHNDC) in two blocks – Nagrota Bagwan and Rait of Kangra district of Himachal Pradesh, where CORD (Chinmaya Organisation for Rural Development), a NGO was actively engaged in rural development. The study utilized a mixed-method approach, combining both quantitative and qualitative research and was conducted between October, 2023 to April, 2024. Ethical approval was obtained from the Institute Ethics Committee of Dr. Rajendra Prasad Government Medical College, Tanda, Himachal Pradesh, registered under National Ethics Committee Registry for Biomedical and Health Research, Department of Health Research, Government of India.

The quantitative study targeted four groups: newly married women, pregnant women, mothers of infants under 6 months and children aged >6-23 months. Participants were selected through simple random sampling, with sample size based on the prevalence of undernutrition in women and children under five in the Kangra district as reported by NFHS-5³ calculated at a 95% confidence level and a 5% margin of error. A 10% non-response rate was accounted for, resulting in a final sample size of 215 for newly married and pregnant women, and 258 mothers for each age group of children (0-6 months and >6-23 months). A total of 3,074 eligible participants were identified across 61 panchayats (local administrative regions), with 34 from Nagrota Bagwan and 27 from Rait blocks. From each panchayat, 3-4 participants were randomly selected, resulting in 949 participants: 215 newly married women, 216 pregnant women, 262 and 256 mothers (total 518) of children aged 0-6 months and >6-23 months, respectively.

Data Collection Tools and Process: For the quantitative study, a structured questionnaire was developed and translated into Hindi, ensuring clarity through pre-testing and undertaking required modifications prior to data collection. The questionnaire covered various domains, including education, family size, maternal and child health (MCH) services, child feeding practices, nutritional status, dietary diversity, sanitation, hygiene, and the utilization of Integrated Child Development Scheme (ICDS) services. Birth weight data was collected either from Maternal and Child Protection (MCP) cards or post-delivery institutional discharge slips and feeding practices were assessed using a 24-hour recall method. Health-related information, such as the incidence of illnesses in the past 30 days, was also recorded.

Nutritional assessments were conducted using standardized methods. For children, weight and length were measured by trained field workers using a digital scale (with 100-gram accuracy) and an infantometer. Z-scores were computed using WHO Anthro software⁴, and nutritional status was classified based on WHO child growth standards, including assessments of underweight, stunting, and wasting⁵. For mothers, weight and height were measured using standardized equipment and procedures. Body Mass Index (BMI) was calculated for newly married women and classified according to WHO BMI thresholds.

Dietary diversity for women was assessed using the Minimum Dietary Diversity for Women (MDD-W) scores, which serve as a proxy for evaluating micronutrient adequacy. This score is based on the consumption of five or more of ten predefined food groups in the previous day. For children aged 6-23 months, the Minimum Adequate Diet (MAD) was assessed, which includes both Minimum Dietary Diversity (MDD) and Minimum Meal Frequency (MMF), based on food group consumption and meal frequency in the previous day⁶. Additionally, based on the dietary recall from the

previous day, consistency of food consumed as well as information on consumption of sweet beverages, packaged savory foods, and other related food items, including any other processed food items, were also recorded.

Data was collected using the Open Data Kit (ODK) platform, with 28 CORD workers trained to use the specific application developed on Android devices. Once collected, data was uploaded to the ODK server, synchronized, and stored for analysis. Supportive supervision was provided by assigning a trained research assistant to each of the two blocks to ensure accurate data collection, and informed consent was obtained from all the participants.

Qualitative Study: The qualitative aspect of the study involved Focus Group Discussions (FGDs) conducted across both study blocks. The groups were composed of 8-10 individuals each, representing: Mahila Mandal members (belonging to families with children under two), male caregivers/fathers, frontline workers from ICDS (Anganwadi Workers/AWWs and *Mukhya Sevikas* (MS)/ supervisors), health workers (ASHAs and ANMs), and *Panchayat* members. A total of 18 FGDs were conducted across the selected areas, guided by an open-ended question checklist. The discussions explored community practices, health and nutrition services, food production and consumption habits, maternal nutrition care, infant and child feeding (IYCF) practices, and social norms around pregnancy, lactation, and IYCF. The FGDs were facilitated by two trained moderators and lasted 60-90 minutes each, with all sessions recorded. Informed consent was obtained from all participants prior to the discussions.

Data Analysis: Quantitative data were analyzed using SPSS (Statistical Package for Social Sciences) Version 23, applying descriptive statistics. Data from the FGDs were transcribed and analyzed thematically to identify key themes and insights related to the study's objectives.

Results

Background Data and Socio-demographic Profile: The survey included a total of 949 participants, with 52.9% from Nagrota Bagwan Block and 48.1% from Rait block. Among the child participants, 53.3% were male and 46.7% were female. The women in the study, aged between 19 and 44 years, were mostly between 26-30 years (46.2%) during pregnancy or lactation. Few women were under 20 years of age (**Table-1**).

Table-1: Background Information of Mothers and the Children

Background Information		Newly married (n=215)	Pregnant women (n = 216)	Children		Pooled sample (N=949)
				0 - 6 month (n =262)	6-23 month (n=256)	
		%	%	%	%	%
Block	Nagrota Bagwan	33.5	56	56.1	62.1	52.9
	Rait	66.5	44	43.9	37.9	48.1
Age of women (in yrs)	≤20	2.8	2.3	0.4	0	1.3
	21-25	50.2	32.9	22.1	19.6	30.2
	26-30	40.5	41.7	52.7	48.0	46.2
	31-35	6.0	17.5	19.5	25.8	17.7
	≥36	0.5	5.6	5.3	6.6	4.6
Age of child* for 0-6 month (in months)	0-2	-	-	21.8	-	-
	3-4	-	-	28.6	-	-
	5-6	-	-	49.6	-	-
	7-12	-	-	-	35.9	-
	13-18	-	-	-	40.2	-
	19-23	-	-	-	23.9	-
Gender of Child*	Male	-	-	53.4	53.1	53.3
	Female	-	-	46.6	46.9	46.7

* n=518

The socio-demographic data (Table 2) reveals that almost all participants (99.9%) were Hindu, with 72.5% belonging to the Other Backward Classes (OBC). Most respondents lived in joint families (80.5%) which were headed by father-in-law or mother-in-law. Housing conditions were generally good, with 95.4% living in pucca houses equipped with toilet facilities.

Among the women surveyed, 96.9% had completed secondary education or higher. A small percentage (0.3%) married before age of 18 years. A significant 92.7% owned a mobile phone. Regarding monthly income, 58.3% of families reported earning over INR 10,000. Most husbands worked in private jobs (44.2%), while women largely stayed at home. 28% of families benefited from the livelihood security scheme, MNREGA (Mahatma Gandhi National Rural Employment Guarantee Act). Regarding community participation, 42% of participants were members of Self-Help Groups, and 49% were part of Mahila Mandals.

Table-2: Socio-Demographic Profile of the Household

Background Information		Newly married (n=215)	Pregnant women (n = 216)	Children		Pooled sample (N=949)
				0 - 6 month (n =262)	6-23 month (n=256)	
		%	%	%	%	%
Religion	Hinduism	100	99.5	100	100	99.9
	Others*	0.0	0.5	0.0	0.0	0.1
Caste	Scheduled Caste	15.3	13.4	12.2	14.8	13.9
	Scheduled Tribe	3.7	7.4	8.4	4.3	6.0
	Other Backward Classes (OBC)	67.4	73.2	73.3	75.4	72.5
	General	13.5	6.0	6.1	5.5	7.6
Type of family	Nuclear	20	24.1	17.6	17.2	19.5
	Joint	80	75.9	82.4	82.8	80.5
Head of Family	Grandfather/ Grand-mother	4.2	6.5	9.2	5.9	6.6
	Father-in-law/ Mother-in-law	94	86.5	81.2	84	86.1
	Others (Brother-in-law/ Sister-in-law/ husband)	1.8	7.0	9.6	9.4	7.4
Educational qualification of women	Illiterate	0.0	0.5	0.0	0.8	0.3
	Primary School/ Middle School	1.9	2.8	2.3	3.9	2.8
	Secondary Education	3.7	7.9	5.7	8.2	6.4
	Senior Secondary y Education	37.2	49.5	50.4	49.6	47.0
	Diploma/Degree Holder	57.2	39.3	41.6	37.5	43.5
Primary Occupation of woman	Housewife	88.4	88.9	89.7	92.6	90.0
	Employed	11.6	11.1	10.3	7.4	10.0
Occupation of Husband	Unemployed	0.5	0.5	0.4	0.4	0.4
	Private Jobs	48.5	42.1	42.7	43.8	44.2
	Government Jobs	20.6	15.3	20.2	14.8	17.7
	Daily wager	14.9	28.2	21	25.8	22.6
	Business	13.1	13.0	15.7	12.8	13.7
	Others	2.4	0.9	0.4	2.4	1.4
Monthly Family Income (INR)	<10000	31.7	47.2	40.1	47.3	41.7
	10000-20000	40.4	30.1	37.4	34.4	35.6
	>20000	27.9	22.7	22.5	18.4	22.7
Others*= Christian Islam, Sikhism, Jainism, Buddhism						

Nutritional Status during the First 1000 Days of Life: The findings of both the quantitative and qualitative studies are presented using the life cycle approach. According to the survey, 21.4% of children were born with low birth weight or at risk at birth (under 2500 grams), while only 22.9% had a birth weight over 3000 grams. The percentage of underweight children (weight-for-age less than -2SD) was higher in the 0-6 months group (44.2%) compared to the >6-23 months group (19.6%). The percentage of stunting (Length/ height-for-age less than -2SD) is comparable in both the groups, with 38.6% of children in the 0-6 month’s group and 37.5% in the 6-23 months group having low height for age. Severe wasting (Weight-for-Height/ length less than -3SD) was observed to be as high as 10.3% in children in the 0-6 months group and 8.6% in the >6-23 months and overweight using this criterion was over 7 % (**Figure-1a, 1b & 1c**). Furthermore, 22.8% of newly married women were underweight, and 12.1% were overweight. Additionally, 34.4% of them weighed less than 45 kg, and 7.4% were shorter than 145 cm. Among pregnant and lactating women, 3.2% of pregnant women and 5.9 % of lactating women (mothers of children 0-6 months and >6-23 months) had a height below 145 cm.

Figure-1a: Underweight (weight for age) among under 2 years children

Figure-1b: Stunting (Length/Height-for-Age) among under 2 years children

Figure-1c: Wasting (Weight-for-Height/length) among under 2 years children

Figure- 2: Breastfeeding Practices and Techniques

Status of Immediate and Underlying Determinants of Undernutrition: The study gathered data on the immediate determinants of undernutrition. Breast feeding (BF) practices for infants aged 0-6 months revealed only 64.5%, of mothers initiated breastfeeding early (within 1 hour of birth), 67.6% mothers reported infants aged between 0-6 months were exclusively breastfed, proper latching was reported in 60.6% of cases, and a very small percentage (6.5%), followed the practice of emptying one breast before switching to the other and making an effort of feeding hind breast milk (Figure 2). Furthermore, 63.7% of mothers followed fixed-time feeding instead of demand feeding (36.3%). The FGDs revealed that while breastfeeding was a common practice, many mothers believed their milk flow was insufficient, leading them to introduce diluted animal milk despite understanding the importance of exclusive breastfeeding (EBF). Many mothers lacked knowledge about proper breastfeeding techniques to improve milk transfer. Traditional myths, such as avoiding breastfeeding in the presence of outsiders or discarding the first milk after outdoor visits, were prevalent and often hindered effective EBF practices.

The data on infant feeding practices for children aged >6-23 months (Figure 3), revealed that 91.8% of mothers continued breastfeeding, with 86% initiating complementary foods between 6-7 months. Interestingly, the percentage of children meeting the minimum adequate diet (MAD) was higher among non-breastfed children (81.9%) than breastfed children (27.8%). Though food diversity was noted to be high, undesirable feeding practices were common, including feeding diluted animal milk (64.1%), thin porridge (88.7%), dal water (83.5%), and rice water (60.5%). Additionally, feeding was often restricted during illness including during diarrhoea and no special effort was made to improve feeding after recovery. Analysis of FGDs also reconfirmed the survey findings on complementary feeding (CF) practices. CF typically began at the recommended age of 6-7 months, but the consistency of food was often watery, such as watery pulses or '*dal ka pani*', watery rice, or diluted milk. The quantity of food items was usually inadequate, and caregivers often did not use separate container or a bowl while feeding, making it hard to track food consumption by a child. While CF practices revealed use of variety of food items, quality protein food sources such as eggs and flesh foods were rarely included. Interestingly, lack of purchasing power was noted to be not issues since resources were commonly used for buying ultra-processed foods like fruit juice, sugary drinks, and potato wafers that were noted to be consumed by 86.3% of families.

Figure-3: Infant and Child Feeding (IYCF) Practices: Children aged >6-23 months (n=256)

Among all women, 89.5 % achieved MDD-W scores, indicating they consumed five or more of the ten food groups. While cereals, roots, tubers, and pulses were consumed in higher amounts, intake of high-quality protein sources like eggs and meat was notably to be rather low. Conversely, the consumption of high-calorie processed foods like sweets, chocolates, ice cream, and packaged snacks was high (Figure 4). FGD findings revealed that food-related taboos and beliefs around hot and cold foods, including cultural restrictions and myths regarding food items like meat, eggs, and ghee, hindered appropriate feeding practices. Additionally, cultural practices such as the priest tying a thread around a pregnant woman (known as “Dora” practice) also influenced feeding behaviors and activity.

A fifth of infants under 6 months (20.6%) experienced fever in the past 30 days, with a higher incidence of 27.7% in children aged 6-23 months. Diarrhoea affected 12.6% of infants in the 0-6 months group and 16% in the 6-23 months group. While 85.5% of diarrhoea cases used oral rehydration solution (ORS) only 56.2% received zinc supplements. Acute respiratory infections were reported in 10.3% of infants 0-6 months and 14.5% of children aged >6-23 months.

Figure-4: Food Intake Pattern of Women (N=949)

The study showed high coverage of health services for women, with 98.4% registering for ANC and a high percentage (91.4%) getting registered in the recommended period of the first trimester. Nearly all mothers (99.6%) reported institutional deliveries, and vaccination coverage for children was also almost universal (99.4%). These findings were supported by FGDs. However, discussions with frontline health workers revealed that key services like regular weighing of mothers, breastfeeding support, and nutrition counselling were not prioritized during ANC visits. The survey also found that while ASHAs were aware of the Home-Based Newborn Care (HBNC) policy and home visit schedule, these visits were rare, and breastfeeding or complementary feeding counselling was not seen as the health sector responsibility. The primary role of Anganwadi Workers (AWWs) was limited to the monthly distribution of supplementary food (SF), with 98.3% of mothers/caregivers receiving SF. Occasionally, AWWs conducted group discussions on nutrition care during pregnancy and complementary feeding by organizing community events such as 'Godh Bharai Days' and 'Annaprasan Days'. Both ASHAs and AWWs recognized the importance of educating mothers on nutrition care and exclusive breastfeeding but did not consistently focus on these actions. Iron Folic Acid (IFA) tablet distribution was well understood to be the responsibility of the health sector. However, consumption rates were seemed to be influenced by fear of side effects such as resulting in jaundice, diarrhoea, or vomiting. No specific effort was made to improve IFA compliance.

The majority of mothers possessed Mother-Child Protection (MCP) cards, but only about one-third ever glanced through or attempted to read these. Neither health nor ICDS workers seemed to engage with mothers on the content of the MCP cards. Unfortunately, the birth weight records of MCP cards and of the delivery discharge slips rarely matched. Furthermore, there was minimal interest in recording or monitoring growth in the charts printed in the MCP cards. The responsibility for monthly height and weight measurements, as well as the recording of supplementary food distribution, was primarily undertaken by the AWWs. Height-weight measures were monthly entered in the ICDS "Poshan Tracker" software. However, examination of the data entered into the Poshan Tracker, during the FGDs, revealed that no child was recorded to be undernourished or of low birth weight though the current survey findings reported a rather high rate of undernutrition in under two. Such a discrepancy noted in the child anthropometric measures need to be urgently and seriously addressed so that the Poshan Tracker does not fail to signal necessary timely home visits and guide actions

FGDs with Panchayats also revealed a unique policy in the state of Himachal Pradesh, where marriage registration is mandatory within 30 days, with ASHAs assisting in the process. ASHAs also distribute folic acid to newlywed women, but no counselling is provided. The panchayat showed interest in using the opportunity of marriage registration for playing a central role in welcoming newlywed women, promoting self-care, and sharing information on available nutrition, health, and family planning services. The data on WASH practices showed 99.1% of households had access to toilet facilities, while 8.9% of individuals practised open defecation. A significant proportion (79.5%) of people washed their hands with soap and water. However, 98.3% of households with children (n=518) dispose of diapers inappropriately, such as throwing used diapers along with the faecal matter in open spaces like rivers or dumping these in soil or burning.

During pregnancy and lactation, most husbands/fathers actively supported their wives by helping with household chores and purchasing additional food, particularly fruits and dry fruits. However, some bought unhealthy processed foods, and a few restricted their wives, as per the existing myths, from eating nutrient-rich items like papaya, chicken, eggs, and ghee.

Discussion

The survey findings reveal that despite positive status of the various underlying determinants of child undernutrition, the rate of child stunting, underweight and wasting rate were rather high. Child undernutrition scenario remained grave despite a very high percentage of mothers completing school education. These findings are in contrast to earlier reports of a decline in stunting rates in children with improvement in underlying factors including increase in education of women (De Onis, 2003, UNICEF, 2022). Child undernutrition was noted to be primarily due to poor pre-pregnancy nutritional status, inadequate maternal nutrition care practices, and inappropriate infant-child feeding practices. Poor nutrition in the pre-conception stage is well documented to contribute to intrauterine growth retardation with a higher incidence of low birth weight⁹ and setting up the life cycle of undernutrition. Prospective study from Vietnam concludes maternal pre-pregnancy weight to be the strongest indicator of predicting infant birth size¹⁰. Women with pregnancy weight of less than 43 Kg or who gained less than 8 kg during pregnancy

were reported to be more likely to give birth to a small for gestational or LBW infant. Today, there is adequate evidence supporting the fact that stunting in children begins in uterus and newborn size is a strong predictor of attaining optimum growth and health¹¹. It is important that both in the preconception and pregnancy period, women are informed of achieving appropriate weight and counselled not only on adequate weight gain and diet diversity but on the benefits of daily consuming high-quality protein food items on birth weight¹² and the significance of being free from anemia. Interestingly, breast milk output in the first three months is not adversely affected by maternal factors¹³ but breastmilk transfer is reported to be not effective if appropriate breastfeeding techniques such as cross cradle hold, latching, feeding hind milk are not followed during the EBF practice (Dalal et al, 2023, Dalal & Vir, 2025). Impact of poor adoption of breastfeeding techniques during “perceived” EBF on child nutritional status is evident from the current study findings with a much higher percentage (45.0%) under six months infants being underweight as against 21.4 % being born at risk LBW.

A high prevalence rate of stunting and wasting reported in the current study in children beyond 6 months could be attributed to feeding CF food items prepared and fed in diluted form due to a strong belief in easing swallowing of food by a child. Feeding such diversified food items, though in diluted form, possibly resulted in high MAD score but such scores were possibly misleading since the recommended MAD assessment methodology does not take into consideration the minimum quantity of any specific food item consumed. Unlike the current finding, high MAD score has been associated with better height and lower risk of being stunted¹⁴. Past studies have also indicated that even with optimum breastfeeding, children will become stunted if they do not receive sufficient quantities of quality complementary feeds after 6 months¹⁵. MAD indicator, a measure of appropriate CF, in such a situation possibly needs to be revisited with reference to inclusion of measure of consistency and defining minimum cut off amount for a food item from a specific food group. The other major gap in complementary feeding practice was noted to be inadequacy in daily feeding of high-quality protein food such as eggs. Suitable time for the introduction of feeding eggs was governed by prevalent strong traditions practices and myths. Daily consumption of eggs by infants 6-9 months has been noted to significantly reduce stunting in young children¹⁶. In vegetarian population, instead of eggs, promotion of regular feeding of home prepared protein rich nutrient dense mixtures could be considered since the beneficial effect on child growth is well documented¹⁷. In addition to these factors, misuse of resources in selection of food items for child feeding was noted with a high percentage of infants being fed unhealthy calorie dense processed food items such as fruit juices, other sugary fizzy drinks, potato chips etc.

The survey findings present evidence that the state policy needs to concentrate for establishing appropriate maternal-infant-young child feeding (MIYCF) practices in the first 1000 day of life as well as in the preconception stage by integrating a package of selected interventions into the current HP state policy entitled “Mukhya Mantri Bal Suposhan Yojana”¹⁸ to achieve the HP state goals of reducing under five stunting prevalence rates to 20 percent and wasting to 10% by 2026.

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Declaration: The manuscript has been read and approved by all the authors, that the requirements for authorship as stated earlier in this document have been met, and that each author believes that the manuscript represents honest work, if that information is not provided in another form.

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